

TO WHAT EXTENT THE DATA AND ANALYSIS INSTRUMENTS, CURRENTLY USED FOR LABOUR MARKET AND SKILLS INTELLIGENCE, ARE FIT FOR PURPOSE?

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ABSTRACT

The accelerating digital transformation across countries is changing the global job market as well as the skills required to carry out those jobs. For being able to timely respond to these changes, governments and other users require more frequent and more fine-grained data for steering skills policies and systems. This paper, through interviews with representatives from international organizations, national governments and other actors, presents a review of the analytical needs of the users of public labour market and skills intelligence instruments. It also provides an assessment of the extent to which the capabilities of existing systems corresponds to those needs. Furthermore, it explores how the emerging "big data" capabilities could help better respond to the evolving needs of users.

KEYWORDS

Decision support, public data systems, skills policy, labour market and skills intelligence (LMSI), online data, linked data

1 INTRODUCTION AND MOTIVATION

In economics, "structural transformations" indicate the changing nature of economic systems, initially from agriculture towards manufacturing and later from manufacturing towards service industries[15]. Accordingly, the types of jobs and skills required to do them are changing too. In line with changing labour markets, also the education systems need to change to be able to provide knowledge and skills responding to the evolving needs[21, 52].

In most of the countries, the task of overseeing these changes and proposing necessary adjustments is delegated to national and/or regional policy bodies - such as labour market and education ministries, regional bodies or dedicated agencies. They are tasked with the collection, analysis and dissemination of labour market and skills data as well as making strategic decisions how education systems should adjust their activities. The collected information may also be used by educational institutions, business or even individuals for more operational or individual decisions[27].

In the past, when the changes have been relatively slow and uniform, the data from statistical surveys and indicator-based reporting, focusing on few key indicators (such as employment or educational attainment) was deemed sufficient to satisfy the analytical needs of the users[20]. This was (and mostly still is) the core of public information systems, providing information for policy makers as well as population at large, to support democratic debate and decision making. However, increasingly rapid technological change as well as deepening job market segmentation and specialisation could both enable and call for new analytical capabilities[52].

For example, insights may be generated from new types of online (as CV and job vacancies) and other data[25, 32]. Evolving digital tools also allows presenting traditional and new forms of data in more targeted and interactive manner, to facilitate analysis and decision making[25]. This could enable analysis which is[20, 35]:

- more detail (e.g. more disaggregated via geographic, occupational or educational dimensions)
- of higher frequency (e.g. beyond annual or quarterly)
- forward-looking (e.g. projections)

Furthermore, a key feature of public data systems is that the producers and owners of the data (e.g. national statistical offices) normally are institutionally separate from the data users (policy makers, researchers or the general public). Safeguarding the confidentiality of data providers as well as independence and impartiality of statistical agencies ensures the integrity of and trust in such systems. Indeed, the independence of institutions producing official statistics is a fundamental requirement of a democratic society, as stated in the principle 1 of the United Nations Fundamental Principles of Official Statistics[4, p. 2]:

Official statistics provide an indispensable element in the information system of a democratic society, serving the Government, the economy and the public with data about the economic, demographic, social and environmental situation. To this end, official statistics that meet the test of practical utility are to be compiled and made available on an impartial basis by official statistical agencies to honour citizens' entitlement to public information.

The separation between data owners and data users, the need to ensure confidentiality as well as the multitude of different data sources and their depositories, constraints the collection and use of data. The process of identification of analytical needs, collection of and access to the data as well as aggregation, analysis and dissemination of data is lengthy and complex. It normally requires collaboration of multiple institutions and specialists, including statisticians and surveyors, data managers, analysts, web design and visualisation specialists, making the process costly and difficult to manage. Confidentiality requirements also limits the content and structure of data that can be made publicly accessible. For previously mentioned reasons, even traditional statistical data is still likely not being used to its full potential[5].

Labour market and skills data systems is an important sub-domain of public data systems. The challenges, evident for overall public data systems, are equally applicable also to this sub-domain. The potential of innovative tools to support the analysis of labour market and skills data is also similarly applicable. This has been demonstrated in recent academic research, including labour market decision support system using online vacancy data[9] or the visual analysis of administrative labour market data[30]. A number of real-world applications, have also been developed, including integrating multiple analytics tools within a single platform, targeted at different types of users.

Indeed, assessing the added value, feasibility and requirements for deploying multiple analytical capabilities (complex, data-driven services) within an integrated analytics services platform was the original motivation for this research project. It was stimulated by the case of SMRT.bio Platform¹, which envisages a ready-made data collection, hosting and analysis system to provide insights and services helping to match skills supply and demand. The system aims to combine data from individuals, employers as well as education providers and is intended to support job-matching processes

¹<https://smrt.bio>, <https://ignitefuture.today>

as well as policy-level steering of the labour market and education systems at local or regional scale. A number of other real world applications are reviewed in more detail in section 2.3.2.

Accordingly, the main problem addressed by this research project is the difficulty in accessing relevant, detailed and timely analytical insights to support decisions of governmental, educational and other entities, with a focus on public labour market and skills intelligence (LMSI) systems. In line with the research problem, the main research question is:

- To what extent existing data and tools for LMSI correspond to the needs of the users and how new data and tools can help better respond to those needs?

To help answer the main research question, several research sub-questions (RSQ) were also set-out:

- (1) What are the main analytical needs of LMSI systems' users?
- (2) To what extent existing LMSI systems address those needs?
- (3) To what extent innovative data and tools can address those needs better?
- (4) To what extent combining multiple different LMSI tools in a single platform could add further value for the users?

The rest of the paper is organised as following. The related work section presents a concise overview of information systems and related research domain. The methodology section introduces the methodology for data collection from interviewees and its analysis. The results section discuss the main findings and observations drawn from the interviews. The discussion section critically reflects and situates the findings in the broader theoretical and practical context. The paper concludes with a summary of the findings, their implications and future research directions.

2 RELATED WORK

This section provides a concise review of key research topics, organised around three main domains:

- business intelligence (BI)/decisions support (DS) systems;
- research on DS, BI and analytics in the public sector;
- literature on the use of data and decision support instruments within labour market and skills intelligence domain.

2.1 Decision support and business intelligence

2.1.1 Decision support systems and decision making. Historically, the link between decision support systems (DSS) and decision making has been framed based on the bounded rationality and phased decision making theory [3] formulated by Simon[53]. The key notions of this work is the distinction between programmed (routine) and unprogrammed (novel) decisions as well as the distinction between three phases of decision making - information search, formulation of possible course of action and choice of a course of action, with a fourth - implementation phase added later.

In addition, a taxonomy of managerial decision making was also developed at a similar time, distinguishing strategic planning, management control and operational control categories[2]. The scope for DSS was then developed based on these two sources, in particular highlighting the different information needs of structured "operational" and unstructured "strategic" decisions, thus also requiring different decision support systems[29].

Furthermore, the theory of the effects of advanced information technology could be useful for understanding the impact of information technologies on organisational design, intelligence and decision making[31]. The theory postulates, that the use of advanced IT systems may help diversify information sources and decision making locations, reduce meetings time as well as enhance organisational memory. As a result, this may lead to more effective environmental scanning, higher quality and faster decision making as well as shorter authorisation time[31].

2.1.2 Business intelligence and analytics systems. As a response to spreading computer technology and growing information volume, since 1990s, a range of new concepts have emerged in the DSS literature. These include business intelligence, business analytics and big data, reflecting the efforts to make better use of these resources[3]. Business intelligence (BI) concept is rather close to the original understanding of DSS[1], but with stronger emphasis on the integration of multiple data sources and their exploitation with data query and visualisation tools[3]. The more recent business analytics concept further highlights the added value of advanced analytical procedures - optimisation, forecasting, predictive modelling and statistical analysis to support decision making[3].

A recent systematic literature review focusing on adoption, utilisation and success (AUS) of BI systems also provide some useful pointers for this research project[1]. It provides a useful overview of the most frequently used theories/frameworks/models, which can be utilised when analysing the success factors of BI system deployment. For example, IS success model indicates that data quality and system quality are the two determining factors for IS adoption[17]. On the other hand, the technology acceptance model (TAM)[16] emphasise the perceived usefulness and ease of use as main factors determining computer use. Overall, the main factors affecting the AUS of BI systems include organisational alignment, adequate IT infrastructure and the importance of user's perspective[1].

2.1.3 Bid data. Most recently, DSS research extended to incorporate the concept of big data. For example, "Big - data, analytics and decisions" (B-DAD) framework explores the role of big data, the required IT technologies as well as the infrastructure to process it ,when applied to each of the four decision phases[18, 19, 49]. Another recent extension is to integrate three elements: (i) the decision phase model, (ii) data acquisition and preparation process and (iii) decision modelling approach[12]. Notably, decision modelling is a method helping to explicitly define the objectives and criteria for specific - high value or critical decision domains such as risk management or fraud prevention, ultimately helping to standardise or even automate the decision making process[55].

2.1.4 Remaining challenges. At the same time, some long-standing challenges remain in the DSS literature, i.e. insufficient grounding in decision-making theory and lack of focus towards strategic decisions domain[3]. Also DSS systems are frequently criticised due to lack of practitioner relevance, configurability and contextual sensitivity[39]. This is often caused by the fact that users are not engaged in systems' design (driven by IT and domain experts). Also the systems are often relatively standardised (lacking customisation), which is required for tailor-fitting the systems to particular contexts and adapting them when the context changes[39].

2.2 Applications in the public sector

While the question of the use of data in governments is not new, the impact of big data and advanced analytics on the public sector is still considered under-explored[46]. This includes limited understanding how to translate the potential of big data into actual value for governments[50]. Multiple pilot exercises and experiments of using big data have already been identified, however in many cases they still largely rely on more traditional - especially administrative - data[48]. This suggests that expectations of big data potential still go far beyond real-world applications and impact[48].

A dominant paradigm for the analysis of policy making process is the policy cycle framework[34, 47]. Also called "stages heuristic", it is a simplified description of policy making as a sequence of stages. In its most basic form, four stages are identified - agenda setting, policy formulation, implementation and evaluation[34]. It is a conceptual tool often used for policy analysis, but being highly simplified it rarely represents the full complexity of reality[34, 47]. Being a staged model, it shares a number of similarities with the phased decision making theory[51], introduced in section 2.1.1.

A recent literature review on the role of big data and advanced analytics in the public sector, highlights the potential of these technologies to contribute to policy making at its different phases[46]:

- in agenda setting and policy formulation phase, it could complement traditional information data sources with faster identification of problems and policy preferences, enable more collaborative policy formation or increase transparency;
- in the policy implementation phase, it could help enhancing public service provision;
- in the policy evaluation stage, it could provide deeper granularity as well as integration of more diverse data sources, thus enabling more powerful and more frequent analysis.

However, it is also recognized, that multiple uncertainties and challenges remain to big data adoption[46]. Privacy (risks of mass-surveillance) and ethics seem to be particularly pronounced challenges, but also inadequate legal frameworks, shortage of skills and resource limitations faced by governments as well as other factors are likely to constraint its adoption[46].

Challenges in ensuring algorithmic accountability[57] are particularly acute. For example, a review of algorithmic decision making within the public sector in the US found it to be increasingly frequently used, particularly at the municipal level[36]. More broadly, the question is how data-driven governance transform traditional governance systems and processes, in particularly as compared to more traditional statistical data[35]. Different from statistics, which are often more about identifying correlate or causal factors of the phenomena analysed, algorithms are more about forecasting, even without clear identification of the drivers of those forecasts[35]. Furthermore, unlike broad categories in statistics, big-data enables much more granular analysis even at an individual level[35].

A separate strand of research focus on the potential and use of analytics and big data at local level government institutions, particularly municipal governments. This research identifies similar challenges associated with the use of big data, including privacy, transparency, data security, data quality or data ownership[37]. Appropriate problem formulation is identified as a critical step for producing meaningful analysis[14].

Several studies review the deployment of analysis and visualisation tools at the city level. A recent review developed a taxonomy of eleven types of such systems [28]. A survey, carried out in Mexico in 2021 and using this taxonomy, found that spreadsheets and institutional systems were the tools most frequently used by government institutions for analytical tasks, with data-sourcing portals and data depositories also being used relatively frequently used. On the other hand, the use of geographic information systems (GIS), computer-aided design (CAD) systems or dashboards was less frequent, while the use of building information or smart city portals rather infrequent. The use of virtual reality or systems with gamification elements (e.g. to make building information systems or navigation of construction projects more interactive) were used least frequently[10].

2.3 Research and applications in LMSI domain

2.3.1 Research and studies. Only a limited number of studies were identified exploring the application of analytical tools for labour market, education or skills data.

One of the papers presents a machine-learning based analytical system and a dashboard for job-vacancy data analysis[8], developed for the European centre for the development of vocational training (CEDEFOP). This system ultimately was integrated into a broader pan-European skills intelligence platform, available online².

A prototype of a somewhat similar system, including web scraping, data mining and spatial segmentation of academic vacancies has also been developed. It confirmed the feasibility of using big data analysis for academic job market, covering multiple countries. It also demonstrated how to present such analysis through a decision support system, including geospatial visualisation solution[9].

A slightly different approach was reported in extracting and modelling company-specific job salary using data for the US from LinkedIn Economic Graph. It was used as a basis of LinkedIn Salary product, allowing users to review potential salaries across job titles, regions and companies as well as the impact of various moderating factors impacting salaries (experience, education, etc.). It included a method to estimate the salary even if no actual observations for that job title, region and company combination were available in the dataset. The solution is reported to have contributed to an increase in the use of the LinkedIn Salary product[11].

A prototype of a system for visualising and data-mining large-scale administrative and normative data on employment contracts and socio-economic characteristics of the persons employed was also developed in Italy . It designed and implemented three visualisations modules: (i) hierarchical data analysis using TreeMap algorithm, (ii) analysis of dynamic and multidimensional characteristics of data using Motion Bubble Chart and (iii) goe-tagged data visualisation as a regional map[30].

Apart from academic research, the use of data and evidence for labour market and skills intelligence has been explored by a number of international organisations and agencies. Multiple policy guides and assessments on how to use big data (particularly the online vacancy data) to inform skills policy were also developed[25, 26, 32, 38].

²<https://www.cedefop.europa.eu/en/tools/skills-intelligence>

This also includes a global, cross-agency stakeholder survey on skills anticipation practices and the use of data and insights for policy development[27], carried out in cooperation of ILO³, CEDEFOP⁴, ETF⁵ and OECD⁶. A similar exercise was also carried out specifically for the OECD member countries[21]. The aforementioned surveys provide a good overview of skills anticipation practices and for what purposes the generated insights are being used by the key users - labour and education ministries. Labour ministries, for example, report to use them most frequently for[27]:

- Updating occupational standards
- Up-skilling or re-skilling trainers
- Develop apprenticeship programmes
- Designing or updating on-the-job training programmes
- Designing or updating re-training programmes

Similar, education ministries report to use skills anticipation most frequently for[27]:

- Updating qualification frameworks
- Updating or designing new qualifications
- Revising or designing new curriculum
- Deciding on the education courses to fund/provide
- For career guidance processes/career counsellors
- For developing or adjusting apprenticeship systems

2.3.2 Real world applications. Despite the shortage of research on the topic, a number of real-world applications have been developed to facilitate access and visualise data on labour market, education and skills at sub-national, national and international levels.

This in particular include various analytical platforms for labour market and skills intelligence (LMSI) in individual countries - UK[41], Jamaica[42] and Kenya[43]. Some countries provide access to detailed labour-market relevant data extracted from administrative data registers, for example information on salaries in Lithuania[7] or labour market and skills forecasts, for example the Estonia[6].

Several analytical platforms cover data from multiple countries for cross-country analysis. These notably include CEDEFOP Skills Intelligence platform[24], UNESCO Skills Panorama for Mediterranean countries[56] and OECD Skills and Jobs database[23].

Other examples include personalised services, such as pan-European career management portal "Europass"[13], "Education and Skills online" skills assessment service from the OECD[22] or skills-based job matching[44] and career guidance[45] portals in Singapore. Finally, SMRT.bio[54] platform aims to combine multiple of such services in a single platform, targeted at regional level.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research gap

As evident from the related work section, the LMSI domain is under-researched. As reported in section 2.3.2, the few available studies largely focus on experimental exercises to build data analysis portals and/or efforts to analyse big data for generating LMSI insights. Only two studies were found to be looking at the purposes, for which LMSI data is used in practice for policy development.

However, no dedicated studies were found to analyse existing LMSI instruments and how these fit users' needs. Similarly, only limited research effort has until now been dedicated for assessing the added value of big data as compared to traditional LMSI data sources. Finally, there is a gap in research on the needs of other types of LMSI users - individuals, companies, general public.

This research project intends to close these research gaps. In particular, it aims to provide a review of the needs of the full variety of users of LMSI and to assess how existing data and solutions fit their needs. In addition, it aims to assess the comparative added-value of new data sources. Finally, it aims to assess the potential and added value of other advanced analytical capabilities, such as linked government data, labour market and skills projections, individualised services and multi-service platforms.

3.2 Approach

For closing research gaps and answering research questions, a qualitative research design was selected. This is due to the shortage of existing research and the need to build understanding of the complex social context in which LMSI is being generated and used.

The primary producers and users of LMSI in contemporary society are expected to be government institutions. They are the societal bodies, which, in response to socio-economic developments and democratic feedback, are mandated to steer education, employment and skills systems. This may cover activities, aiming to affect the supply of skills (e.g. through education services), the demand of skills (e.g. through industrial development programmes) and the systems for matching skills supply and demand (e.g. ensuring transparency and efficacy of labour markets). Indeed, existing research suggests that the main users of LMSI throughout the world come from education and labour ministries[27].

Accordingly, the persons best placed to provide information on the use of LMSI in policy making process are officials from government bodies and other organisations (e.g. social partners)[27], involved in the development of labour market, education and skills policies. Furthermore, existing research and practical examples suggests that international organisations are also actively involved in generating and using LMSI. Finally, persons involved in developing LMSI tools are also expected to be aware of users' needs as well as the limits/shortcomings of those tools. Thus the overall target population can be defined as experts, who deal with the production and/or use of LMSI for policy development.

For collecting the required information, semi-structured interviewing was selected as the most appropriate research method. Interviewing was judged as the most adequate research method given that it allows gathering the perspectives of users from different countries and institutions (e.g. using digital communication tools). At the same time, it retains the necessary depth of information to be collected. Alternative methods, such as in-situ observation, would be much more restrictive in terms of generalising findings and hard to implement in practice due to often sensitive nature of policy development process. On the other hand, more structured approaches - such as fully structured interview or expert survey would likely limit the depth of information collected. It would also be difficult to reach adequate sample sizes due to small size and wide spread of the target population across many countries.

³<https://www.ilo.org/global/topics/skills-knowledge-and-employability>

⁴<https://www.cedefop.europa.eu/en/themes/learning-anticipate-and-match-skills>

⁵<https://www.etf.europa.eu/en/practice-areas/skills-future>

⁶<https://www.oecd.org/els/emp/skills-and-work/changingskillsneeds/>

3.3 Interview content

Each interview consisted of three main sections: (i) an introductory section, discussing the background of the interviewee; (ii) a section focused on existing/traditional data and capabilities; and (iii) a section focused on emerging/new capabilities. In summary, the interviews covered these main broad topics:

- (1) Which are the most important data and instruments used for labour market and skills intelligence (LMSI)?
- (2) Who are their main users?
- (3) For what purposes do they use it?
- (4) What are the main drawbacks of existing instruments?
- (5) To what extent and which new big data capabilities are being used (including complex systems for analysing, visualising or communicating data/analysis)?
- (6) Which of the emerging capabilities are most interesting?

Each of these broad topics link to a specific research sub-questions (RSQ), stated at the beginning of this paper. Notably, topics 1-3 provided data for answering RSQ-1, topic 4 for answering RSQ-2, topics 5-6 for answering RSQ-3 and RSQ-4. These broad topics were further sub-divided into more specific interview questions.

3.4 Interview planning

For planning the interviews, a detailed interview guide has been prepared, including the background of this research project and the list of questions to be addressed during the interviews, shared with interviewees before the interviews. In addition, an interview protocol was designed to help manage the interview process.

The interview guide and protocol was tested in a pilot interview with a person not directly related to the project. The final interview guide and protocol was produced taking into account all the received feedback. The information provided in the interview guide, e.g. background information as well as the full questionnaire are available respectively in Appendix A and Appendix B; interview protocol is available in Appendix C.

3.5 Interviewee sampling and response rate

Interviewees were sampled using a mixture of purposive and convenience sampling methods. Given the specificity of the domain, only a limited number institutions and specialists are involved in labour market and skills intelligence activities. For the interviews, as explained in section 3.2, three main groups of users were identified - national level policy experts, international level policy experts and specialists involved in developing LMSI tools. From the latter group, some were from businesses, while others - from academia. Thus, ultimately, four categories for classifying interviewees were used: national policy, international policy, business, academia.

From literature as well as previous professional experience of the author, a number of international organisations engaged with skills policy and LMSI were identified. These includes the ILO, the OECD, European Commission, UNESCO and CEDEFOP (see also section 2.3.1). Eight persons, known to be dealing with skills policy and LMSI, were contacted from these organisations, mostly working in labour market, education or skills policy departments. Their contact details were available to the author from earlier professional work.

Furthermore, it was decided to reach out to experts, who have experience in national skills policies, representing a wide range of

countries. This included experts from Austria, Estonia, Hungary, Lithuania, South Africa, Singapore and Spain. This aimed to ensure that the views represent countries of different sizes, levels of economic development, types of governance arrangements (decentralised - Austria and Spain v/s centralised - the rest). This also enabled to capture experiences from countries with known elaborate LMSI systems in operation (elaborate citizen-facing portals in Singapore and elaborate administrative data systems in Austria and Estonia). Six experts, known to have been exposed to LMSI systems in these countries and mostly working in or with the ministries of education, were contacted. Their contact details were available to the author from earlier professional work, with one exception, in which case contact details were provided by SMRT.bio company.

Finally, representatives of three private sector organisations (who have experience developing LMSI systems/portals) as well as representatives from two academic institutions (with background in information systems and education research domains). In total 6 persons from these organisations were contacted, with the contact details identified and reach-out facilitated by SMRT.bio company. From 21 experts who were contacted (contact included the request for participation and the provision of the interview guide), 17 experts responded positively to the invitation.

During interviews, it also appeared that some interviewees have experience in multiple types of organisations. Thus, overall, interviewees represented well the different types of actors involved with LMSI. Out of 17 interviewees, six have current or past experience in academia, six have experience with skills policy at national level, nine have experience with skills policy at international level and four have experience from business perspective. This is also in part a conservative assessment, as majority of experts engaged at international level, as part of their responsibilities, often analyse, provide advice or design interventions in collaboration with national governments, academia or businesses. For a full overview of the background of interviewees, please see figure 2 in Appendix D.

3.6 The execution of interviews

The interviews were carried out between May and June, 2022. All interviewees agreed for the interview to be recorded. All except one interviews were carried out in English, the remaining one carried out in Lithuanian. Most of the interviews lasted around one hour, from the minimum of 43 minutes to the maximum of 1 hour 24 minutes. All interviews were carried out online and recorded using Zoom online conferencing software. Due to technical problems, the recording of one of the interviews has failed, but the main points of the interview were noted in writing.

4 RESULTS

The overall goals of the analysis was to answer the main research question - to what extent existing LMSI capabilities correspond to users' needs and how innovative capabilities could help respond to those needs better. Four research sub-questions (RSQs) were used to help answer the overall questions. RSQ-1 and RSQ-2 were focused on answering the first part of the question - identifying users' needs and assessing the extent to which they are satisfied with existing LMSI instruments. On the other hand, RSQ-3 and RSQ-4 were focused on the second part of the main research question and

looked into the potential of innovative analytical capabilities. As mentioned in section 3.3, each RSQ was then linked to a particular part of the questionnaire, with the final questions formulated so that they provide information to answer the respective RSQ.

4.1 Interview transcription and coding

For the analysis, interviews were transcribed using automatic transcription function of a paid version of Descript software⁷. Interview coding was subsequently pursued using the open coding approach, by re-reading the interviews and in case of doubt re-listening relevant expressions. The concepts and ideas identified in the interviews were coded using standard Excel environment. The automatically transcribed text was in most cases understandable, but of mediocre quality. When in doubt, Descript software provides for a convenient way to select and re-listen the original recording of a particular word or expression. However, the transcription of the interview carried out in Lithuanian language was of very low quality, thus the coding had to be done by re-listening the whole interview. Due to time limitations, automatic transcriptions of the interviews were not further corrected. To preserve interviewee identity, introductory sections as well as any references allowing to identify the interviewees were removed from the transcripts. The copies of anonymised automatic transcripts of the interviews can be accessed here: <https://www.dropbox.com/sh/iicez9xdqiwlre6/AACBsuhnm2opd7uBucAnFY1fa?dl=0>.

The final list of themes, used for coding the answers in the interviews, can be found in Appendix E. Below the the most frequently mentioned categories for each of the thematic section of the questionnaire are detailed. The full list of categories, identified during the interviews, can be found in the Appendix F.

4.2 User's analytical needs

The purpose of this part of the questionnaire was collect information in order to answer RSQ-1, i.e. what are the main analytical needs of key users of existing LMSI systems. This was done by inquiring about main LMSI users, main data sources and producers of those data as well as the content of data used.

4.2.1 Main users. The very first issue tackled in the interview was identification of main user groups. The most frequent user group indicated was national governments (mentioned by 8 interviewees) and various educational institutions (mentioned by 7 interviewees). International organisations, regional governments, social partners and individuals were each mentioned by 6 interviewees. Other more frequently mentioned categories were career councillors, companies, academic researchers, specialised agencies (e.g. qualification bodies), local governments, consultants/trainers.

4.2.2 Purposes of use. In terms of purposes for which LMSI is used, the most frequently mentioned categories were planning the volume of education provision (7 interviewees), policy purposes (including for drafting policy documents/briefings, policy development, policy evaluation - 6 interviewees), for financial/investment planning (5 interviewees), for career counselling (5 interviewees), for educational quality assurance/school management (4 interviewees), for tracking graduates (4 interviewees).

⁷<https://www.descript.com/>

4.2.3 Data producers. In terms of data producers, national governments (including statistical agencies) were mentioned most frequently (10 interviewees). International organisations were also frequently mentioned (7 interviewees), though more as institutions aggregating data collected at national level. Another prominent category of data producers were companies (6 interviewees), particularly in relation to production of online data.

4.2.4 Data sources. In terms of data sources, the majority (12 interviewees) mentioned statistical population surveys (primarily labour force survey). Many (10 interviewees) mentioned online data, but often in the context of experimentation or interest, rather than regular use. Another highlighted source of data was administrative data, including education (6 interviewees), tax/social security (6 interviewees) or unemployment data (4 interviewees). Other mentioned sources included company surveys (5 interviewees), specialised surveys like graduate, job satisfaction or skills surveys (4 interviewees) or specific studies (3 interviewees).

4.2.5 Data content. Finally, in terms of content of data used, most frequently mentioned categories included skills, though sometimes indicating low use of such data due to data limitations and the use of proxy measures such as education or occupation (8 interviewees), online job vacancy data, though again often more as aspirational, rather than actual, use (8 interviewees), employment/unemployment (7 interviewees), income (7 interviewees), occupation (7 interviewees), educational background (6 interviewees), online CVs (6 interviewees), graduate tracking data (5 interviewees), vocational/career interests and aspirations (5 interviewees) and geographic/location data (5 interviewees). Many other types of data content were also mentioned, with a total of 32 categories ultimately used for coding different data content types.

4.2.6 Summary assessment - users' needs. These results broadly confirm earlier findings that main users and producers of data are government institutions and that traditional data sources are still dominant. However, the range of the types of users reported is broader than expected, as well as the importance given to such users groups as educational institutions, social partners and individuals. Another observation is high diversity of data content, potentially reflecting the real-world complexity of the domain.

4.3 Factors affecting data use

The purpose of this part of the questionnaire was to collect information for answering RSQ-2, i.e. to what extent the existing capabilities of LMSI systems answer users' analytical needs. This included identification of the shortcomings of existing LMSI systems and challenges faced in balancing skills supply and demand. This was done by inquiring to what extent LMSI is used to help match skills supply and demand and what factors inhibit its use. The information provided by interviewees on challenges faced using LMSI for balancing skills supply and demand, were broadly grouped into two categories. The first include factors directly related with data quality, accessibility and practices of use. The second include factors driven by structural features of education and labour market systems (e.g. education adjustment costs and constraints) and unrelated to data quality or availability.

4.3.1 Data-related challenges. From the first category, most frequently mentioned issues were limited institutional capability (5 interviewees), lack of data granularity (4 interviewees), absence of governance bodies linking education and labour market (4 interviewees) and the importance of having capacity to react to forecasts (4 interviewees). Other categories, indicated by 3 interviewees, include data being good on providing headline figures but lacking actionable information, lack of awareness of what data is available and challenges collecting information from migrants.

4.3.2 Systemic challenges. From the second category, interviewees also indicated that better (or even ideal) data in itself would not be sufficient to solve the challenge of aligning skills supply with demand. This includes various delays and constraints in adjusting education supply (mentioned by 4 interviewees), economic cycles and crises (3 interviewees), fluidity of individuals' career choices (3 interviewees), overall complexity of phenomena, which is difficult to be comprehensively represented with data (3 interviewees), migration, particularly cross-border (3 interviewees).

Also, several respondents indicated that in some situations data on skills demand may not be even considered of relevance. This may apply in case when education policy is driven by other socio-political considerations rather than the skills/labour demand paradigm. For example, when the policy intention is to increase the overall level of education of the population, or to increase the supply of certain skills even in the absence of demand (thus creating an imbalance), in the expectation that this will help later attract foreign investment and create new jobs. It may also apply in situations when there is a general shortage of employment opportunities, or when available employment opportunities are not sufficiently attractive. In such cases, education may be provided in support of emigration and helps reduce labour over-supply within the country, as is observed in some of the developing economies.

4.3.3 Summary assessment - challenges. These findings largely confirm the expected shortcomings of traditional LMSI as lacking granularity, data access difficulties, challenges with data production. However, unexpectedly, the most prominent categories were related to the institutional capacity to use the data as well as the ability to act upon data insights. A useful distinction was identified between data use for "headline" communication and for taking real action, pointing that existing LMSI is broadly adequate for the former, but not the later. Responses also confirm that policy makers face challenges due to the ongoing changes. However, the importance assigned to the structural constraints they face when reacting to those changes is rather unexpected. Finally, the emphasis on the limits of skills supply-demand matching paradigm in some socio-political contexts, suggests low relevance of LMSI in such situations.

4.4 The potential of innovative capabilities

The purpose of this part of the questionnaire was to collect information for answering RSQ-3, i.e. to what extent can emerging big data and other advanced capabilities better respond to users' needs. This included discussion on the actual use of innovative capabilities, the drawbacks and benefits of two alternative sources of data to traditional statistics - big data and linked administrative data as well as the most promising capabilities to develop in the future.

4.4.1 Use of innovative capabilities. In terms of innovative capability use, those mentioned most frequently include forecasts/projections (7 interviewees), individualised advice - though often indicated as aspirational (7 interviewees), online vacancy data - though often indicated as experimental or ad-hoc (6 interviewees), linked administrative data (6 interviewees) and data visualisation (6 interviewees).

4.4.2 Big data. As regards the benefits and drawbacks of big data, the benefits include high granularity (4 interviewees), timeliness, sample size, cost, ability to track rapid developments and fit for skills demand monitoring. As for the drawbacks, these include lack of comparability - over time, between countries, or to other statistics (7 interviewees) and lack of representativeness (6 interviewees).

4.4.3 Linked data. For linked data, only 8 respondents had more extensive exposure to such systems. As its benefits, they indicated low cost (2 interviewees) and longitudinal nature (2 interviewees). Other indicated benefits were timeliness, good coverage, large sample size, representativeness, quality, granularity and the breadth of information available (e.g. economic, company, sectoral data). For the drawbacks, the main one was challenges in actually linking separate datasets (4 interviewees), the need for involvement of external entity (statistical office) for actual matching (2 interviewees) and lack of availability in developing country context.

4.4.4 Future capabilities. Among the more forward-looking needs and capabilities, the most frequently mentioned issue was the challenge and the need to ensure that the data represents reality more comprehensively, i.e. better integration and presentation of multiple data sources and data dimensions for the analysis (5 interviewees). Other avenues for future exploration include collection of data on individual career interests, enabling access to data analysis as a service as well as exploring data from learning analytics and educational content. The need to better explore data source linkage for data generation and extraction, as well as enhancing the capacity to manage linked data ecosystems was also mentioned.

4.4.5 Summary - innovative capabilities. These findings indicate that innovative capabilities analysed in this paper are already rather broadly (though not necessarily intensively) used. Interviewees confirmed the expected limitations of big data as well as the expected benefits of linked administrative data. What was more interesting, was the emphasis on the value and fit of big data for monitoring rapidly changing situations and in particular at a detail geographical level. In this domain, this may for example be applied when designing short-term training programmes for well defined shortage occupations. Useful indications were also provided on the challenges analysing and interpreting administrative data, given that there may be lack of documentation on the coverage, definitions used or the process of data collection.

4.5 The potential of integrated platforms

The purpose of this part of the questionnaire was to collect information for answering RSQ-4, i.e. what is the potential for deploying a range of analytical capabilities within an integrated platform. This was done inquiring interviewees about the experience (if any) dealing with such platforms, their features and challenges faced.

Only 10 respondents had more extensive exposure to such systems. Those who did, highlight as the most prominent issues the potential of more individualised consumption of data (5 interviewees) and technical challenges of designing such platforms (5 interviewees), though often stating that the latter are generally solvable. The importance of clearly defining target users and a good understanding of their needs was also mentioned (4 interviewees).

A number of other issues were also mentioned, such as usage as a key determinant of platform success, inherently limited number of government users, lack of uptake of existing systems by individuals and employers, the importance of identifying the most appropriate user groups as well as highlighting simplicity and ease of access as key requirements. Finally, integration of additional services was often mentioned, for example financial incentives for education and training, educational and job offer.

These findings highlight the need to ensure broad platform usage to ensure its success. Interviewees also indicated that platforms targeting exclusively or primarily policy users may be hard to justify given small number of potential users. On the other hand, designing platforms for use by broader population is challenging as it requires attracting and retaining a critical mass of users in a rather competitive environment. Potential lack of use is also a challenge, given that individuals consider more significant career changes only rarely and often need to find a job quickly, rather than embarking on longer-term career planning and retraining.

5 DISCUSSION

This section provides a critical reflection on the key findings emerging from the interviews, their links with issues discussed in the literature as well as what implications this have for the design of different LMSI instruments and data sources. The findings are underpinned by a selection of quotations from the interviews, which can be found at the relevant sections in the appendix G

5.1 The use of LMSI

This section mainly refers to results as reported in section 4.2 and the implications for RSQ-1, i.e. the needs of LMSI users’.

5.1.1 Diversity of users and their needs. The first observation as regards the use of LMSI is the diversity of users of such data or systems (see section 4.2.1) as well as differences in their data needs and requirements (see section 4.2.2). On the one hand, there are large institutional users (notably governments, educational institutions or consultancies) and, on the other hand, individual persons or small companies. While the former are few in number, they have significant data analysis capacities and interest in looking at a broad range of data. They need reliable, aggregated and representative data. The latter are large in numbers, but limited in the time they can spend for analysing information. In between, there are regional or local level actors who need sufficiently detailed, but still aggregated data (see interview quotes in the appendix G.1.1).

5.1.2 Different data accuracy requirements. Secondly, different decision making contexts (see section 4.2.2) have implications for data coverage, accuracy or representativeness requirements, which has implications on the types of data sources which can be used. For example, institutional users are often interested in using data which

covers, in aggregated form, many topics and dimensions. They also need certainty that data is representative, of high quality and can be trusted, given the often high-stakes of the decisions to be made. Similarly, for a young person, a decision to select a particular career or educational pathway calls for breadth and trust of information to be used for such decision. Conversely, when choosing jobs to apply, if a job search query provides an individual with a large portion of job advertisements which are not relevant; or an employer deciding whom to invite to interview receives a list of CVs some of which are not very attractive, this has only limited implications for the user (see interview quote in the appendix G.1.2).

5.1.3 Emphasis on operational use of LMSI. Interviews indicate that the most frequently cited purpose of LMSI use (see section 4.2.2) is operational, e.g. for planning and steering the provision of education services. This includes tasks like planning the financing, quantity and content of education provision as well as arranging various instruments (standards, performance agreements, quality assurance processes) which help governing education systems, a finding applicable despite the economic development level of a country (see relevant interview quote in the appendix G.1.3).

There were also references to the use of LMSI for broader policy development and evaluation. These findings align with the major models of institutional decision making, identified in the literature: the division of decisions between strategic and operational (see section 2.1.1) as well as staged decision making models applied to business (see section 2.1.1) and policy (see section 2.2) contexts.

5.1.4 Relevance of institutional context. There are clear differences in the propensity to use data depending on the type of institution and its context (see section 4.2.1). Among government bodies, international organisations seems to be most intense users of data, as one of the main instruments to reach out to their stakeholders. National level governments, even if being the main producers and owners of data, seems to be less frequent users. Regional and local level governments may be keen to use data for solving practical problems, but are often restricted from doing so due to capacity and data availability constraints (see first interview quote in the appendix G.1.4). The use of data for educational planning purposes also depends on the political context (see second interview quote in the appendix G.1.4).

5.1.5 Selective use of evidence. A number of the interviewees also highlighted the selective use of evidence, such as choosing the types of information which fits policy narrative, supports what was done or what is intended to be done (see relevant interview quotes in the appendix G.1.5). This seems to connect to the literature in strategic management studies, where some authors propose to conceptually separate (the mostly informal) social and political process of making strategic decisions from the role of more formal, data-driven and analytical strategic planning[40]. In such perspective, data and formal planning is used to help rationalise, negotiate and communicate strategic decisions as well as control their implementation[40]. This also links to the literature in the domain of management information systems, where some authors suggest that management information serves not so much to inform the managers for making a decision, but rather to improve their capacity to negotiate and implement decisions through social and political processes[33].

5.2 Barriers to the use of LMSI

This section refers to results as reported in section 4.3 and the implications for RSQ-2, i.e. the drawbacks of existing LMSI tools.

5.2.1 LMSI is not "actionable". When asked about the extent to which LMSI are fit for purpose (see section 4.3.1), interviewees remarked that it may depend on the type of use in mind. For example, existing data seems to be good in enabling the production of headline figures (GDP, employment), also allowing assessment of the performance over time and across countries. However, existing data and instruments lack details to make such data "actionable". In particular, the limits of granularity of traditional survey-based statistics is notable (an issue also identified by the OECD[21]), there are also limits to what it covers (see relevant interview quotes in the appendix G.2.1).

5.2.2 The challenge of skills matching. A fundamental prerequisite for making a data-driven assessment of skills supply and demand match is the availability of analytical and empirical categories allowing such linkages. However there exist both technical as well as conceptual challenges in linking the two - from outdated, inadequate categories (an issue also identified by the OECD[21]) to a general problem of identifying an appropriate or inappropriate match (see relevant interview quotes in the appendix G.2.2).

5.2.3 The challenge of the forward-looking view. While a large number of interviewees referred to the value of future-oriented projections (see section 4.4.1), this was also perceived as tricky to be used. Available data almost always refers to the past, sometimes with a significant delay. Forward-looking projections and simulations may help situate the implications of decisions and may help monitor progress. However, they are difficult to produce, are inherently uncertain and may reveal lack of capacity to enact change (see relevant interview quotes in the appendix G.2.3).

5.2.4 The challenge of data synthesis. Given the diversity of sources (see section 4.2.4) and content (see section 4.2.5) of data, used for LMSI, it would be very useful to see all relevant information in an integrated manner. Even for individual forecasts, depending on the assumptions used, one can get different estimates. The question how best to present multiple dimensions from different data sources, including forward-looking projections and uncertainty, remains open (see relevant interview quotes in the appendix G.2.4).

5.2.5 The limits to planning. Even if having perfect information, skills mismatches are likely to persist[21]. There are multiple constraints, both internal to education system and external to it, that inhibit or delay its adjustments to changing demands (see section 4.3.2). These include costs and delays implied by any adjustments to education systems, constraints to increase supply in growing fields, fluctuation in the labour market due to economic cyclicality, crises (like Covid-19) or technological change. Governments also rarely intervene to steer the demand for skills, making supply adjustments largely reactive (see interview quotes in the appendix G.2.5).

5.3 The potential of new capabilities

This section refers to results as reported in section 4.4 and the implications for RSQ-3, i.e. to what extent can emerging analytical capabilities better respond to users' needs.

5.3.1 Big data. Many constraints were mentioned as regards the quality and access to big data (see section 4.4.2). It is particularly challenging for low-income countries where most job vacancies and job search (especially in informal employment) is not covered by such data. As a result, the use of such data, despite already being available for some time, has remained sporadic or experimental (see relevant interview quotes in appendix G.3.1). However, this data still holds some potential if used for monitoring rapidly changing situation and in response designing quick interventions, such as short term training programmes (see section 4.4.5).

5.3.2 Linked administrative data. During the interviews, particularly with national level policy makers from economically advanced countries (i.e. Austria, Estonia, Singapore), administrative data was perceived as a promising source of information. On some key dimensions it can be comparable to survey-based data, such as being representative, while on other dimensions it can even surpass it, such as quality, timeliness, exhaustive coverage of the whole target population. Among the key drawbacks, the ones most often cited were technical issues of data linkage and data analysis process (see section 4.4.5). However, its most critical issue seems the inherent absence of qualitative information. Another key issue is that only few most administratively advanced countries are in a position to use such systems (see interview quotes in appendix G.3.2).

5.4 The potential of integrated platforms

This section mainly refers to results as reported in section 4.5 and the implications for RSQ-4, i.e. what is the potential for deploying a range of advanced analytical capabilities within an integrated platform. It is notable, that only part of the interviewees have been exposed to such systems (see section 4.5). This may be explained by the fact that interviews focused on exploring the use of data and LMSI systems by the public-sector. Therefore, only limited amount of feedback was received during the interviews as regards the potential of such instruments.

As regards platforms designed for or by public sector institutions, they face some inherent challenges. On the one hand, if intended to be used by the public sector, due to inherently small number of potential users it may be difficult to justify the resources for developing such systems. On the other hand, when developed by the public sector but targeting general population as users, competition with existing private platforms becomes a key challenge. Overall, appropriate targeting and good fit with users' needs as well as achieving a critical scale of usage is required to make such systems work (see relevant interview quotes in appendix G.4.1).

5.5 Answering the main research question

This section provides a full synthesis of the findings and the implications for the main research question, i.e. to what extent existing LMSI data and tools correspond to the needs of the users and how innovative solutions can help better respond to those needs.

What concerns the first part of the question, in most cases, the adequacy of public LMSI instruments for the main groups of users is considered to be low (see Figure 1). In addition, one could also argue that in certain contexts, notably low-income countries, LMSI instruments may overall have only low relevance. One exception is the use of such data by governments for policy development.

User group	Type of use	Example of need	Level of use	Adequacy
Individual persons	Strategic	Career choice	Almost none	Low
	Operational	Job search	Use private solutions	N.A.
Individual companies	Strategic	HR planning	Mostly internal data	Low
	Operational	Candidate search	Use private solutions	N.A.
Educational institutions	Strategic	Strategic planning	Only if autonomous	Low
	Operational	Service planning	Only if autonomous	Low
Governments	Strategic	Policy development	Selective	Moderate
	Operational	Service planning	Mostly internal data	Low

Figure 1: LMSI systems adequacy, by user type and purpose

It is also notable, that for some operational uses, such as job-matching or job candidate selection, the traditional notion of LMSI may not be applicable. Those services, often provided within the private sector, work more like ranking or search algorithms, rather than as sources of aggregate and representative information about the status of the labour market. Thus, for the operational needs of individuals or companies (i.e. for job or candidate search), public LMSI systems may not be fully relevant or applicable. Nevertheless, a combination of job-search function with some aggregated information from public or private sources (e.g. expected salary, working conditions) could be useful, as testified by the solution to provide estimated salary information, developed by LinkedIn (see section 2.3.2 for more detailed discussion).

For the second part of the main research question, i.e. the potential of new capabilities to enhance the value of LMSI, the findings can be summarised as follows:

- Big data sources (notably online vacancies and CVs), at this stage seem to have only limited potential for application, except for some narrow, well-defined contexts like identifying most popular programming languages and designing short-term training programmes based on those;
- Linked administrative data has potential in countries with sufficiently developed administrative data systems (particularly in the education, taxation and unemployment domains), even if various technical and analytical challenges remain;
- Data visualisation solutions are likely to be relatively easy to deploy, but being more applicable to operational level they depend on the maturity of data systems;
- Targeted data communication systems are still largely at experimental stage; also even more so than data visualisation solutions, they depend on the adequacy of underlying operational data;
- There are very few examples of integrated platforms that provide services both to individual and institutional users. One can't deny the viability of such platforms, but it seems that currently existing solutions usually select one of those broad target groups as the main focus.

5.6 Limitations

A number of limitations need to be considered when interpreting the findings of this research. First of all, the limited number of interviewees can not represent the full diversity of systems or institutions across countries. Thus generalisability of the findings needs to be understood with caution.

Furthermore, even if efforts were made to reach out to experts from both developed and developing economies, respondents coming from most developed economies were significantly over-represented. This is also a result of structural reasons - LMSI instruments and data collection tools are more advanced and more broadly used in such countries, as compared to developing economies.

In addition, one of the limitations was the focus on public LMSI tools, thus the analysis did not include private sectors platforms (such as LinkedIn). Extending analysis to such systems and the services they offer could also provide additional insights.

Furthermore, the scope of the interviews did not allow to get into detail on the type of specific LMSI tools (i.e. databases, dashboards) being used (for an example of such studies see section 2.2).

Another major limitation, observed when coding the answers, was that interviewees often qualified their answers, i.e. indicating that a certain type of data is used frequently or, alternatively, infrequently. The used coding scheme as well as interview protocol was not sufficiently detailed to be able to adequately capture this. For future research, it may be useful to foresee avenues how data on such additional dimensions could be collected and coded.

The validity of research findings could be further enhanced by at least two ways. One way would be re-doing the coding of the interviews by several researchers at the same time to test for inter-coder reliability of the coding scheme. Another avenue for testing the validity of the findings would be to organise a focus group with some of the interviewees to validate and discuss the results.

6 CONCLUSION

6.1 Summary of key findings

When trying to answer the ultimate research question - to what extent existing LMSI systems correspond to the needs of the users of such systems, it appeared to be useful to differentiate the types of users and their needs. In terms of use of LMSI systems by governments, there seems to exist a major disconnect between two major decision and data domains: operational decision domain, primarily oriented towards internal financial and administrative data and policy domain, oriented towards macro-level statistical data. One could argue that both of these domains face data use challenges. For example, policy level is challenged by the breadth of data and the problem of its synthesis; the operational level is challenged by the lack of actionable details in the available data.

For other types of users - individuals, companies or educational institutions, existing public LMSI systems do not fit their needs very well, primarily due to the absence of data granularity. Accordingly, such users likely use such systems only sporadically. One also needs to take into account that for operational needs of individuals and companies, e.g. job or candidate search, there exist multiple private solutions and platforms. Thus any effort to design public LMSI systems that would aim entering this market would need to take into consideration private sector competition and the resulting higher user acquisition and retention costs.

Finally, among emerging capabilities, policy users in advanced economies over the medium term are likely to benefit more from the evolution of linked administrative data systems rather than big data systems (e.g. online vacancies or CVs). On the other hand, LMSI systems in developing economies may need to rely on traditional

data (if available at all) and also must consider to what extent investment in such capabilities are relevant in their socio-economic and policy context. Over the short-term and whenever at least some data are available, different visualisation solutions is the easiest and fastest capability that can be deployed.

In terms of practical implications, the findings of this study may be relevant for various entities. In particular, this may be public sector personnel involved in planning, design and management of public LMSI systems. This would also apply to those involved in the overall steering of public data systems within the labour market, education and skills domains. It may also be useful for other organisations, such as SMRT.bio, involved in the design of LMSI systems targeted at the public sector and/or other users groups. Finally, it may be useful for organisations designing internal data analytics instruments, potentially even beyond the public sector.

6.2 Future work

The findings from this study also give some orientation of possible directions for further research. Over the short-term, this may include a more thorough review of existing public LMSI platforms globally, their business models and usage levels, potentially including linked open government data initiatives. Another, more medium-term research agenda could further look into how linkage and/or alignment of administrative data with statistical survey data could help breach the data granularity barrier. This could be applicable not only at a national level, but also for some international organisations, such as European Commission, which also likely possess an abundance of administrative data from its public investment programmes. Finally, as a longer-term challenge, there is a need to better understand what are the conditions and enablers, including access to relevant information systems, which would help individuals to take a more strategic approach to their career management. Some other avenues of future research, also indicated by interviewees, include data synthesis, learning analytics as well as the challenge of managing linked data ecosystems.

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Appendices

Appendix A INTERVIEW GUIDE: BACKGROUND INFORMATION

Background: this interview will be carried out by Mantas Sekmokas⁸, a student at the Master's degree programme in Information Studies at the University of Amsterdam (UvA)⁹. The results of the interviews will be used to inform a research project, leading to a final Master thesis titled "Assessing labour market and skills intelligence (LMSI) analytics systems for decision support: a case study of the SMRT.bio "CockpitWork" big data analysis tool". This research project is carried out under the guidance of SMRT.bio Global.

Research objectives: the accelerating digital transformation across countries is changing the global job market as well as the skills required to carry out those jobs. For being able to timely respond to these changes, governments and other actors may require more frequent and fine-grained data for steering labour market and skills policies and systems¹⁰. The focus is to analyse an innovative big data analysis tool – CockpitWork, which enables rapid collection and fine-grained analysis of data for labour market and skills intelligence (LMSI)¹¹. More specifically, this research project aims to assess the extent to which this tool corresponds to the needs of prospective users.

Appendix B INTERVIEW GUIDE: QUESTIONNAIRE

A: Introduction

- Could you shortly describe what is your professional background?
- How comfortable are you in general about the topic of data and analysis?
- And how comfortable are you about the topic of labour market/skills intelligence?

B: Existing capabilities of labour market/skills intelligence

- From your perspective, which LMSI data and instruments are the most important?
- Who are the main users of those instruments and for what purposes do they use them?
- To what extent you agree that the primary purpose of skills intelligence is to adjusting the volume of training programmes?
- What do you think are the main obstacles for broader/more effective use of LMSI?
- In particular, what do you think are the main issues facing:
 - Data acquisition?
 - Data analysis to generate insights?
 - Ensuring that insights are actionable?
 - Use of insights for decision making?
- Is your field of work related in any extent to labour market/skills intelligence? If yes:
 - What is the relation?
 - For what purposes such intelligence is used?
 - What type of analysis is being used (descriptive; relational; experimental; etc.)?
 - What is the level of such analysis (e.g., cross-national; national; local; etc.)?
 - What kinds of data are being used (e.g., statistics; administrative; big data; etc.)?
 - What tools/software are being used to manage and analyse the data?
- Do you use labour market and skills data in your work? If yes, what do you think about:
 - The availability of such data?
 - The coverage of such data?
 - The granularity of such data?
 - The identifiability of such data?
 - The accessibility of such data?
 - The quality of such data?
 - The timeliness of such data?

C: Big data capabilities for labour market/skills intelligence

- In your opinion, to what extent big data capabilities are already being used for labour market/skills intelligence?
- When talking about big data capabilities, what do you think about the use of:
 - Innovative data sources (i.e., job ads, geospatial, mobile, social network data)?
 - Innovative data collection tools (i.e., apps, passive data collection)?

⁸<https://be.linkedin.com/in/sekmokasmantas>

⁹<https://www.uva.nl/en/programmes/masters/information-studies/information-studies.html>

¹⁰In this research project, labour market and skills policies are presumed to cover policy domains aiming to affect the supply of skills (through e.g., education, training or employment policies), the demand of skills (through e.g., industrial transformation or enterprise support programmes) and the systems for matching skills supply and demand (through e.g., greater transparency and efficacy of skills markets)

¹¹Labour market and skills intelligence refers to the various data acquisition and data analysis activities to inform decisions for steering labour market and skills policies and systems.

- Interactive visualisations/dashboards?
- Projections/forecasts?
- Back-casting techniques?
- Machine-learning/AI techniques for individual level prediction?
- Are there any other big data capabilities you could think of?
- Which of these capabilities do you find most promising? Why?
- Which of these capabilities do you find most challenging? Why?

Appendix C INTERVIEW PROTOCOL

- Expression of gratitude for interviewees availability;
- Confirmation of the time available for the interview;
- Notification that the results of the interview will be kept confidential and will be used only for this research;
- Request for consent to use interview results for this research;
- Request for consent to record the interview.
- At the end of the interview, requesting interviewee about availability and interest for a follow-up and expression of gratitude for the interview.

Appendix D INTERVIEWEE BACKGROUND

Interviewee	Research	National	International	Business
I1	x	x	x	
I2				x
I3				x
I4		x	x	
I5	x		x	
I6			x	
I7	x		x	
I8		x		x
I9		x		
I10	x		x	
I11		x		
I12	x			
I13				x
I14			x	
I15		x		
I16			x	
I17	x		x	

Figure 2: The background of the interviewees

Appendix E THE FINAL LIST OF THEMES, USED FOR CODING THE ANSWERS

For answering RSQ-1, i.e. what are the main analytical needs of key users of existing LMSI systems, the interviewees' answers were grouped under these categories:

- The main users of relevant data/instruments;
- The main purposes for which instruments are used;
- The main producers of relevant data;
- The main data sources and analysis instruments;
- The main content/categories of the data being used;

For answering RSQ-2, i.e. to what extent the existing capabilities of LMSI systems answer those analytical needs, the interviewees' answers were grouped under these categories:

- Main issues with existing data and instruments;
- General challenges of matching skills supply and demand;

For answering RSQ-3, i.e. to what extent can emerging big data and other advanced capabilities better respond to users' needs, the interviewees' answers were grouped under these categories:

- The big data capabilities that are used or of interest;
- The benefits of big data;
- The drawbacks of big data;
- The benefits of linked administrative data;
- The drawbacks of linked administrative data;
- Avenues for future development.

For answering RSQ-4, i.e. what is the potential for deploying a range of advanced capabilities within an integrated platform, the interviewees' answers were grouped under these categories:

- Features and challenges of integrated multi-user platforms;

Appendix F FULL LIST OF CODES

The list of final codes, used for coding the interviewees, is provided below. The number next to the code indicates how many interviewees mentioned the coded concept during the interview.

F.1 Users

- Government - national (8)
- Government - regional (6)
- Government - supranational (6)
- Individuals (6)
- Schools (6)
- Social partners (incl. unions, professional associations, chambers, sectoral bodies, etc.) (6)
- Career, employment counsellors (4)
- Academic research (3)
- Companies (3)
- Education/qualification agencies and other spec. bodies (3)
- Consultancies and trainers (2)
- Government - local; city-level (2)
- Universities (for planning provision) (2)
- General public (1)
- Learners (1)
- Non-formal education providers (1)
- Project level (for promoters; funders) (1)
- Teachers (1)
- Youth (1)

F.2 Type of use

- For planning education provision quantity (7)
- Career counselling/individualised advice (5)
- For financial/investment planning (5)
- Education quality assurance; school management (4)
- Graduate tracking (4)
- For designing new programmes (3)
- For planning education provision content (3)
- Identify shortage/priority occupations (3)
- Individual job matching (3)
- Academic research (2)
- Citations in documents (briefings; policy documents) (2)
- Design outcome based funding/performance agreements (2)
- For benchmarking (e.g. cross-national data) (2)
- For policy development (2)
- For steering/advising other actors (2)
- Planning apprenticeships (2)
- To evaluate policy implementation/impact evaluation (2)

- Check assumptions (1)
- Conditional development support (1)
- Design occupation standards (1)
- For setting up new schools (1)
- Planning retraining by public employment services (1)
- To justify policy changes (1)

F.3 Data/evidence producers

- National government (incl. agencies, statistical offices) (10)
- Supranational (7)
- Specific companies - big data (6)
- Sub-national government (2)
- Academia (1)
- Consultancies (1)
- Educational institutions (1)
- Sectoral bodies (1)
- Specific companies - employment services (1)

F.4 Data sources

- Surveys of general population (esp. LFS) (12)
- Online data (incl. LinkedIn, online vacancies) (10)
- Administrative - education data and registers (6)
- Administrative - social security/income/tax and registers (6)
- Surveys of companies (5)
- Specialized surveys (graduates; job satisfaction, etc.) (4)
- Administrative - unemployment/public employment services data and registers (3)
- Sectoral studies (2)
- Thematic studies (2)
- Digital labour platforms (1)
- Focus groups (1)

F.5 Data content

- Online vacancies (8)
- Skills (incl. int. skills assessments) (8)
- Employment and unemployment (7)
- Income (7)
- Occupation (7)
- Level, field of education, education programmes (6)
- Online CV's (6)
- Geographical disaggregation (location data) (5)
- Graduate tracking/school-to-work transition (5)
- Vocational interests/preferences, career aspirations/expectations (5)
- Admin learners, study duration, and financing (4)
- Enterprise data (3)
- Industry/sector of economy (3)
- Working conditions (3)
- Added value (2)
- Demographic data (gender/sex; age) (2)
- Economic data (export; investment) (2)
- Educational text data (curriculum; program descriptions) (2)
- Job tasks (2)
- National assessments (2)
- Applicants to educational programs (1)
- Constraints of business activities (1)
- Data on qualifications, training providers (1)
- Drop-out from education (1)

- Education process data (1)
- Educational trajectories (1)
- Job satisfaction (1)
- Labour migration (1)
- Personality tests (1)
- Product/service pricing (1)
- Skills match (1)
- Socio-economic background (incl. migrant, mother tongue) (1)

F.6 Usage of new capabilities

- Forecasts/projections (7)
- Individualized advice (educational/career) (7)
- Linked admin data (6)
- Online vacancies (6)
- Visualization (6)
- Individualized matching (jobs; education; etc.) (4)
- Taxonomies (ESCO, O*NET, other national) (4)
- Emerging software/ solutions (3)
- Estimating long-term impact of AI/automation (2)
- Foresight (qualitative) (2)
- Gap analysis: forecast v/s policy objectives (2)
- Planning for economic development (2)
- Social media data (2)
- Traditional software/solutions (2)
- Use mobile phones to collect data (2)
- Linked admin and survey data (1)

F.7 Challenges with existing LMSI

- Institutional capability to produce and use data (5)
- Capability to take action against forecasts (4)
- Lack of details, granularity (4)
- Presence of consultation/governance bodies (4)
- Awareness what is available (3)
- Good on headline figures, bad on actionable details (3)
- People's mobility is a challenge for monitoring (3)
- Clear institutional responsibility set (2)
- Clear purpose of data/analysis (2)
- Data accessibility/fragmentation (2)
- Data collection costs, especially for developing countries (2)
- Data literacy (general) (2)
- Difficulty in adjusting data collection (2)
- Ensuring data comparability (diversity of input) (2)
- Feedback on usefulness of data (policy; research) (2)
- Large number of different actors and diversity of needs (2)
- Awareness of benefits (1)
- Balancing internal v/s outsourced (1)
- Change of underlying structures over time (1)
- Confidentiality (1)
- Data is too technical (1)
- Data understandability (1)
- Delays in adjusting data collection (1)
- Delays in producing analysis (1)
- Difficult interpret data (multiple interpretations possible) (1)
- Disproportional data collection costs in non-urbanized countries (1)
- Ensuring that data is representative (1)
- Hard to measure benefits of analytics (1)

- Information delays (1)
- Lack of actionability (what to focus on) (1)
- Lack of detailed data on graduates (1)
- Low political visibility of analytics (1)
- Misuse (exaggeration) of causal claims (1)
- Political economy (1)
- Poor macro-regional level data (1)
- Relevance of occupational classification (ISCO) (1)
- Resource burden producing disaggregated data (1)
- Separation of financing and outcome responsibilities (1)

F.8 Big data benefits

- High level of detail (4)
- Easier to reach large sample size (2)
- Increasing coverage (2)
- Timeliness (2)
- For matching no need to have exhaustive information (1)
- High geographic disaggregation (1)
- Indicate skills in demand - high-paying; frequent (1)
- Low cost (1)
- Tracking rapid developments (1)
- Use for designing short-term training; reskilling (1)
- Vacancies useful to monitor demand evolution (1)
- With rapid data needs; crisis (1)

F.9 Big data challenges

- Comparability (cross-country; over time; to other stats) (7)
- Lack of representativeness, selection bias (6)
- Access restrictions (3)
- Black box approach (3)
- Coverage - unclear, in developing countries - only urban; white collar (3)
- May be too detailed (aggregation challenge) (3)
- Unreliable - outdated, biased, created for other purpose (3)
- Added value beyond traditional sources (1)
- Arbitrary methodology (for aggregation) > lack of trust (1)
- Country specific terminology (1)
- Cross-domain transferability (1)
- Defining the unit of measurement (stock v/s flow) (1)
- Duplication (1)
- Insufficient internet access may be an issue (1)
- Lack of systematic classifications (1)
- Limited number of dimensions covered (1)
- Low accuracy at granular level (occupation; educational attainment) (1)
- Qualitative dimensions (beyond skill/occupation) (1)
- Short time series (1)
- Validity/reliability (1)

F.10 Benefits of linked administrative data

- Longitudinal form; track trajectories/pathways (2)
- Low cost (2)
- Company information (1)
- Coverage (1)
- Economic data (1)
- Level of detail (1)
- Quality (1)
- Representativeness (1)

- Sample size (1)
- Sectoral information (1)
- Timeliness (1)

F.11 Drawbacks of linked administrative data

- Linkage (absence; legal issues, agreement of diff owners) (4)
- Coverage of rural; informal employment in dev. Countries (2)
- Matching done by dedicated entity (NSI) (2)
- Absence of qualitative data (1)
- Choose appropriate time-frame (1)
- Coverage of emigrants (1)
- Coverage of foreign qualifications (1)
- Different data structures difficult to align (1)
- Individual registers may have coverage issues (1)
- Limitations if some key dimension is absent (1)
- Linking with regional data (1)
- May be difficult to understand/counterintuitive (1)
- Need clear awareness of limitations (1)
- Only in few countries well developed (1)

F.12 General issues of matching skills supply and demand

- Constraints/delays to adjust supply (incl. cost) (4)
- Economic cycles, other changes inhibit planning (3)
- Financial incentives help with participants (3)
- Foreseeing individual choices (3)
- Migration (3)
- Overall complexity/dimensionality of phenomenon (3)
- Difficult to judge which mismatch is bad (2)
- Employer engagement in decision making; curriculum design (2)
- General educational delays (2)
- Informality of job markets and employment in developing countries (2)
- Interest v/s steering for career guidance (2)
- Occupational standards (2)
- Oversupply of skills (2)
- Short-term training (incl micro-credentials) (2)
- Skills shortage due to lack of job attractiveness (2)
- Absence of information on demand (1)
- Actionable recommendations (1)
- Aligning occ. classifications (ISCO) and occ. standards (1)
- Competence-based approach/curriculum (1)
- Cross-border recognition of qualifications (1)
- Cross-institutional collaboration and trust (1)
- Decision feedback loop (1)
- Decision making delays (1)
- Dedicated bodies non-functional (1)
- Different specificity of different fields/levels of education (1)
- Difficult for youngster to decide what to do (1)
- Digital labour platforms (1)
- Disconnected education and employment/economic policy (1)
- Financial constraints to steer the system (1)
- Geographic distribution of training locations (1)
- Impact of technological change/AI (1)
- Inflation of educational credentials (1)
- International political economy (1)
- Job shortage (1)
- Lack of steering of skills demand/employment (1)

- Low jobless benefits may raise mismatch (1)
- Market-driven steering mechanisms (apprenticeships) (1)
- Modular provision of training (1)
- Performance agreements (1)
- Regulated professions and other occupations (1)
- Salary and working conditions (1)
- Sufficiently broad training for flexibility (1)
- The speed of change (1)
- Training is tuned towards big employers (1)

F.13 Issues with integrated tools

- Individualize consumption of data analysis (5)
- Technical challenges (5)
- Identify users and their needs (4)
- Integrating educational offer (3)
- Integrating financial incentives (2)
- Integrating job offer (2)
- Simple/easy to understand data (2)
- Usage is a key criterion (2)
- Awareness of potential benefits (to invest) (1)
- Capability to engage the right users (1)
- Infrequent use by individuals and employers (1)
- Limited number of users in government (1)
- Simplify data accessibility (1)
- Very low error tolerance in guidance, policy advice (1)

F.14 Avenues for future development

- Holistic/comprehensive approach (5)
- Building analysis as a service (2)
- Learning analytics (2)
- Need for data on individual interests (2)
- Educational text mining (1)
- Gamification of data collection (1)
- Industrial and skills planning aligned with interests (1)
- Managing linked data ecosystem - corrections, quality (1)
- Need for faster adaptation of education (1)
- Need for forward-looking educational guidance (1)
- Need for long-term vision of employers (1)
- Need for projecting future skills gaps (1)
- Need to focus on regional level (1)
- Need to focus on SMEs (1)
- Rethinking combination of data sources for data generation (1)

Appendix G INTERVIEWEE QUOTATIONS

G.1 Quotations on the use of LMSI

G.1.1 Diversity of users and their needs. Quotations:

Interviewee 5: when you run skills intelligence [in a cross-national context], these have a certain type of function. So to broadly have indications about, okay, what are the overall implications of the greening of the economy <...> you have to have an idea of the implication overall. Then you have to go at the different levels - national level and then local level to understand the actual implications.

Interviewee 14: I think we have to distinguish the cross country comparable information and also the country or region-specific information. And in terms of the cross country, comparable information, I think UIS and also ILO and OECD they have already been doing <...> excellent in terms of the cross country, comparable education, statistics, and data. But when we try to give policy advice to specific country, <...> you

have to collect the [country] specific information.

Interviewee 6: We want to present intelligence that could be useful for people's career decisions, that gives them things like what occupations or skills are most useful or where those skills are in demand in regions or countries <...>. These are not people who are gonna care about the context or all the sort of you know, contextual information around it. They really just want in a very simple form, useful information.

G.1.2 Different data quality and content requirements. Quotation:

Interviewee 5: The problem is that it works because even if I receive five, I mean, out of 10 advertisements, nine wrong and one right. Okay. For them is, is fine because the important is they reach out me with the one right advertisement and I buy the product. That they were wrong nine time for them, and for me, no harm, I mean, no problem. If I have to provide <...> the user with information about, uh, that relevant in terms of guidance for your job and whatever. I cannot give you nine wrong information and one right.

G.1.3 Emphasis on operational use of LMSI. Quotation:

Interviewee 16: I think in the education space, it's got, gotten a lot better. The usage, you know, for planning purposes, Because education is mandatory and there's a lot of processes and support for this in low and middle income countries and lots of administrative data being produced to then assess students and their levels and also for managing schools. And then I don't know that as well, but that's definitely much more advanced than let's say employment related data, like job creation, jobs, anticipation skills, anticipation, labor force planning, reducing the skills mismatches and stuff like that. I think we're only at the really start of that.

G.1.4 Relevance of institutional context. Quotations:

First quotation:

Interviewee 1: for OECD, for ILO and all these people, if they want to engage their clients, which are governments often, then they use anything that they can get a hold of and including creating their own. <...> They far more serious, they take it right. So they, you see more use in there at that level. And the exploitation of data is more okay. <...> I have seen regional governments that taking this more seriously than national government. <...> it kind of a little bit more permanent often than the, you know, the narrative headline grabbing one, the national governments, if it fits into a particular party's narratives. <...> So the extent of use probably expect a little bit more, but I also see that regional government has less resources than national government, less to play with.

Second quotation:

Interviewee 1: For the market economy like the UK and US, there is an assumption that education and training is the responsibilities of the employer. <...> So the lack of engagement and in most cases they say market will sort it out. Then you don't need data can be what's wrong, you know, it's there, they'll sort it out.<...> The theoretical argument is they should use more of solid evidence if you can, or as solid that you can. But in reality, I think what is much driven is the way that a political culture and believe in philosophy is behind it. That will make a big difference in terms of that kind of use.

G.1.5 Selective use of evidence. Quotations:

Interviewee 1: Most governments actually don't actively fund research for their policy making. They tend to come across them. They use their advice. And so on, they pick up the narratives, which is a result of research, somewhere, that fits what they did.

Interviewee 11: I think it's from case to case, but of course also let's say the political level, they also have some preference for "policy based evidence".

G.2 Quotations on the barriers to the use of LMSI

G.2.1 LMSI is not "actionable". Quotations:

Interviewee 1: At one level, they, government is in a good place, but then, they're not actionable in terms of what policy to make. It doesn't give you details. As an example, labor force survey, or other returns from employers and so on often give them aggregates. They're pretty

good that for, you know, big kind of headline things like GDP growth and things like that, they're in a good place. <...> So actionable details, mostly big data labor force survey don't give you anything. It really there's nothing tell you should do this, or you should do that. You should now focus on soft skill or allow you to focus on, uh, employ protection.

Interviewee 6: First of all, as regards to skills intelligence, as you know, it's largely by proxy, you know, we're talking about looking at occupations and demand and so on and, and looking at ISCED for supply of skills, you know, we're not really looking at people's skills levels directly by and large.

G.2.2 The challenge of skills matching. Quotations:

Interviewee 8 (translated): For example, the classification of occupations, based on ISCO classification, it is programmed to be outdated and to differ from the reality. I am not sure if it is avoidable, but because it's a top-down process, or lacks consultation with practitioners/employers and is being designed in high-level groups, companies then have trouble understanding it. In reality workers do not identify with some of those professions as they are described. There are also duplications, it is a bit of a muddle there and it's not clear how to sort it out, especially at the national level.

Interviewee 15: Some people in a way, try to present the information in a way that there should be exact match. You studied, since you can't do anything else, you have to do the same. So my opinion is that you can't do it because there are a lot of very good examples that people who studied something are very effective in, in another job or in another sector.

G.2.3 The challenge of the forward-looking view. Quotations:

Interviewee 5: We want a certain future is not a prediction. It's a wish. This is the role of the policies because otherwise, okay. You can leave the market to go and we will see what is the future. We don't need to predict; if we need to predict, because we want to shape the future. And so when you shape the future, then what matter is to try to see the implications for our policy. To ensure that we go in the right direction or that we go in there in a good way. So this is this type of understanding that, first of all, it is not easy to do it, but it's also not easy understood by the policy makers.

Interviewee 10: Maybe giving that prediction is not always helpful, especially you think about the individual one. I mean, if you take a disadvantaged black kid in a disadvantaged suburb in the US, the strongest prediction might be that they will be jailed by the age of 25 and shot dead by the age of 30, that prediction is not very helpful.

G.2.4 The challenge of data synthesis. Quotations:

Interviewee 5: we have these different approaches because we feel that there is not a single type of skills intelligence that can give answers to what we want. The point on which we are trying to make an effort now is okay, developing the individual pieces, but also working on, find out how to combine in a meaningful way, the different sources or the different estimate. This is in my view, one of the major challenges that we have today in our work, because for instance, you can have the forecast to see the overall trends. But through the skill service, you can identify, for example, what current jobs are more likely to be automated, and then you can combine the two things, with an overview of what is likely to happen in the future, in the labor market.

G.2.5 The limits to planning. Quotations:

Interviewee 4: I would say one, this is something that all the governments wish it was possible. Like this they tell us how much they need, and then we produce those kids, but it, that never happens like that.

Interviewee 10: [Supply constraints] is a huge constraint. I would say that, it's a major if you issue, because basically whether you look at vocational schools or higher level institutions, there is very strong inertia to do the same they were doing last year. They have the right teachers, they have the right equipment. They have the right classroom settings, number of seats, plan curriculum, author, like if you need to be certified to do something. So institutions have very strong incentives to do exactly what they were doing last year. And of course, if, if we're looking at high demand occupations, it will be particularly hard to find a new teacher. <...> And, of course, if you're in a high demand occupation, chances are you get a very good wage working in the industry. So going to teach in a school is not going to be very attractive.

Interviewee 14: if the country is providing TVET or training in a sense by modular basis, like Finland, I think they may be able to modify the quantity of training in a relatively flexible way. <...> But in many low-income countries, their system is not that flexible. They cannot make

changes of the number of teachers and also the number of schools and the curricular. So I don't think they can adjust the quantity of the training to the changing labor market needs immediately. <...> I don't want to be too pessimistic <...> but I don't think in a short term they can adjust to the labor market needs immediately, but for the midterm and long term, of course, they should be able to make some adjustments.

Interviewee 15: The key point is that we can analyze data and we can think what is the best number for the new entrance or how many new people should start to study on this sector or that, but at the end of the day, people are making the choice and this is so far, it is on a voluntary base. So how you can influence, of course there is, there are always more popular occupations to start to learn. <...> and what we are, we are doing is just to follow the trends.

Interviewee 16: but it's also difficult to, to use [the data] because it's difficult to do labor force management and planning, based on economic development, economic growth, and it's the challenge even for rich countries to do that. It's difficult, I think, because there's just a lack of jobs, production overall in a lot of these countries. So we always know that supply is gonna far outweigh the demand in all of these countries. So then what can you do, do you even need some of this data and planning tools?

G.3 Quotations on the potential of new capabilities

G.3.1 *Big data.* Quotations:

Interviewee 1: And the problem with it is that the methodology let's say a taxonomy of skills is arbitrary, always arbitrary. And the tech key people who produces have no domain knowledge and they could not justify the actions of it. So immediately the policy makers, the minister and all that kind of, oh wow, dear. And they're not gonna use it. And then the next thing is they could not justify how representative the data is. So if it is not representative, it's just good, big, attractive, so on whatever and volume trying to drag out everything. Okay. And immediacy means that it's real time, but real time and volume doesn't charm everything. Every politician has to be cautious about representative. In fact, there's one big killer is never been used.

Interviewee 14: I think it [job vacancy data] gives us some implication regarding what kind of, yes, how the curricular should be adjusted and also what kind of new training we should be provided and if it is challenging to change the curriculum of the formal training systems, I think it can give some suggestion regarding what kind of short term training they need to provide in order to meet the demand of employers immediately. <...> I think it makes more sense for the use of the [job vacancy data] for, for example, the upskilling and reskilling of those who are already in the labor market and who maybe lost their jobs and they, who needs to find a job very quickly.

G.3.2 *Linked administrative data.* Quotations:

Interviewee 7: I think government administrative data can be great. <...> I think this is great because it combines large sample size, which is the issue with, with some sample surveys, also it tackles the representativeness issue. I mean, depending on the type of data, but often it is quite comprehensive. So, yeah, I think administrative data is great. And I think there's a couple of Nordic countries are great. The Netherlands is great. The US is very good. And then a lot of other countries are a lot less good.

Interviewee 11: Advanced is the linking of registers. And this is the thing where we at the moment put most efforts in, it has its limitations and for many users or want to be users of the data, it's difficult to understand the data. And when we have results, they are sometimes, counterintuitive. We have to think a lot on it. So this is still more in an experimental phase. <..> Actually, we don't have a lot of experience with interpreting this, this kind of data and many users let's say who are not so familiar with data, they have not really adequate expectations.

Interviewee 14: I think if it is a formal employment, I think we we can try to collect, information and also we can make use of the existing available information as much as possible, including from the government and authorities, and also from the enterprises, including the SME organizations or those kind of things. But for the informal sectors, informal means they are not registered and they may not, you know, pay taxes. So, it's really difficult, but, I think we can think about conducting a survey [for these people].

Interviewee 15: This interlinkages [of administrative data] you say would be the main one. We follow labour force survey, of course, as well. And the linking, I don't believe we need any additional sources, but of course, we are participating in PIAAC, because, you know, you get additional variables in this case. And of course you can link PIAAC with tax board as well and that kind of things, what we are planning and different registers. So it's, whatever it is, what gives more insight. But you can dig in and you can look but sometimes qualitative information is needed as well in a way to get the information about why people are doing [things]. <...> But, but the link qualitative information set kind of surveys with administrative data is a tricky thing. <...> because you, you okay. PIAAC is big enough to work on this and to get

permission from people that we can link information.

G.4 Quotations on the potential of integrated platforms

G.4.1 The potential of integrated platforms. Quotations:

Interviewee 1: So in general, this labor market tool, is that low utilization by the users is the biggest problem. <...> Now, if it was an open market that one [education] provider can steal the learners from an adjacent stage that they will make use of tools like that they'll make use of tools that look at learners, behavior, job seekers, behavior, what they want, what they need. <...> People come to knock on my door because you are creating a market in there. The integrated environment essentially is greater a market now. <...> So, so far the biggest challenge is still not as many employers as the government would like it to be using it, some using it and using it for the reason I explained, and individuals only do it when they feel in their crisis in their life, they turn to it. <...> So until they have a crisis in their life, a need that has to be met and these needs doesn't come on a daily basis.

Interviewee 2: [It is] a platform that is focusing on two main subjects, personal development and economic development with a goal to mobilize all of the talents and assets in a given region where we are combining the four key stakeholders on the labor market in one coherent platform where the goal is to do your little dance as a micro, SME or as an individual or as a region or an education institution, and allow the platform to make meaningful connections between the four key stakeholders.